

THE USE OF ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN LITERARY CONTEXTS

Usmonov Muso Usmonovich

Candidate of philological sciences, Associate professor of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract. The present article is devoted to the analysis of the contextual peculiarities of English phraseological units, their stylistic abilities and pragmatic functions.

Key words: phraseological unit, metaphoric meaning, stylistic mean, pragmatic function, contextual realization.

INGLIZ FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARINING BADIY KONTEKSTDA QO‘LLANILISHI

Usmonov Muso Usmonovich

Filologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz frazeologik birliklarining kontekstual xususiyatlari, ularning stilistik imkoniyatlari hamda pragmatik funksiyalarini tahlil qilishga bag‘ishlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: frazeologik birlik, metaforik ma‘no, stilistik vosita, pragmatik funktsiya, kontekstual realizatsiya

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКИХ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ В ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОМ КОНТЕКСТЕ

Усманов Мусо Усманович

Кандидат филологических наук, доцент, Самаркандский государственный институт иностранных языков

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена анализу контекстуальных особенностей английских фразеологических единиц, их стилистических возможностей и прагматических функций.

Ключевые слова: фразеологическая единица, метафорическое значение, стилистическое средство, прагматическая функция, контекстуальная реализация

In the following context, the same image and its theme are emphasized by cohesion, that is, the appearance of equivalent elements in equivalent positions. Moreover, equivalence of positions can be understood broadly; it can occur at all levels. In the story, the officer's observations of the bridgehead fortifications and the evacuation across the bridge are combined with the mention of the old man still sitting in the same place.

An old man with steel rimmed spectacles and very dusty clothes sat by the side of the road. There was a pontoon bridge... (p. 311)... over the bridge. There were not so many carts now and very few people on foot, but old man was still there (p. 311)... I was watching the bridge... and the old man still sat there (p. 312).

From the perspective of expressiveness created by means of prominence, i.e., the aesthetic ordering of the context, the first phrase in this chain is interesting because it repeats information in two strong positions.

These strong positions are the title and the first phrase of the text. The fact that the reader's attention should linger on these places in the text is explained by the laws of speech prediction.

Probabilistic prediction is the ability of a person to use information from their past experience to predict the likelihood of certain events occurring in an upcoming situation.

The mechanism of probabilistic prediction presets the brain for text perception. Experiments have proven that the brain continuously generates ongoing speech predictions. The title and first phrase of any text form the starting point of a new series of predictive operations. Hence their great importance, and therefore these positions are called strong.

In this case, expressiveness is doubled due to the two strong positions. The content of the title is repeated and expanded in the first sentence of the story:

Old Man at the Bridge: An old man with steel rimmed spectacles and very dusty clothes sat by the side of the road.

The expressiveness created by subsequent repetitions emphasizes not only that the old man has not yet left the dangerous spot (the bridge is bound to be the site of some military operations), but also that he is unable to leave—he is too exhausted.

This semantic repetition builds steadily throughout the story. First, there's the mention of dusty clothes. This piece of information allows the reader to reconstruct what was left unsaid – the old man had to trudge along the dusty road for a long time.

Subsequently, the old man's fatigue is no longer directly stated. The protagonist understands that the old man sits motionless because he is too tired and unable to walk any further.

The very first dialogue between the officer and the old man introduces the mention that not only is the old man's clothes dusty, but his face is also dusty and gray.

As the conversation continues, when the officer sees that the old man has not yet left and asks him whose side he is on, the old man simply replies:

«I am without politics. I am seventy six years old. I have come twelve kilometers now and I think I can go no further».

Over and over, the officer insists that the old man should leave, but the man only looks at him wearily and continues muttering about the animals he left behind and his concern for them. The officer, aware of the danger, continues to insist, and here comes the climax:

«Thank you», he said and got to his feet, swayed from side to side and then sat down backwards in the dust.

The story's composition is built on the interweaving of several themes, expressed through repetition, within a minimal textual space. The result is a paradoxical combination of extreme conciseness and repetition. A series of repetitions depicts the initially intense, then diminishing, flow of wagons carrying the retreating army and refugees, creating a dynamic effect. This flow serves as a kind of background.

There was a pontoon bridge across the river and carts, trucks, and men, women and children were crossing it. The mule-drawn carts staggered up the steep bank from the bridge... (p. 311).

*There was not so many carts now and very few people on foot... (p. 311).
...watching the far and of the bridge where a few last carts were hurrying down the slope of the bank (p. 312).*

I said, watching the far bank where now there were no carts (p. 313).

The story's structural completeness and coherence are striking. It has much in common with lyric poetry. Its central theme is the understanding of human suffering, personified in the figure of a simple old man.

The hero's extreme tension and his concern for the old man are expressed through subtext. At the same time, the old man's anxiety for his helpless animals is expressed through a series of repetitions:

«I was taking care of animals» (p. 311).

«I stayed, you see, taking care of animals. I was the last one to leave the town of San Carlos» (p. 311).

Animals make the main theme of the dialogue between the character and old man.

Expressive repetition is vivid at the end of the story:

«I was taking care of animals», he said dully, but no longer to me.

«*I was only taking care of animals*».

Caring for animals is the most peaceful of human activities. The word "only" in the old man's final words is especially poignant—he had done no harm to anyone, only looked after the animals.

In the conversation about animals, disappointed expectations were once again the signal of expressiveness. When asked again (again, a repetition) what kind of animals they were, the old man replied that there were only three—two goats and a cat, and four pairs of pigeons. This unexpected answer, in contrast to the gravity of the military events, doesn't create a comical effect. On the contrary, it is pathetic. The unfortunate, lonely, very poor, and utterly helpless old man worries about creatures even more defenseless than himself. He is somewhat comforted by the fact that the cat can take care of itself, but he dreads the thought of what will happen to the others. For the officer, the phrase about the cat sounds like bitter irony: the cat can take care of itself, but the old man cannot.

The moment of the enemy's appearance is getting closer and closer. Against this backdrop, the reader perceives the mental states of two people—the old man and the officer. Despite their differences, they also share something in common. Both are exposed to danger, but each thinks not of themselves, but of the other. The story ends with an unexpected resolution – a point, a slightly aphoristic ending, and a bitter irony.

Literature:

1. Jackendoff R. Foundations of Language. Brain. Meaning. Grammar. Evolution. – Oxford: University Press, 2004. – 477 p.
2. Labov William. Principles of Linguistic Change: Social Factors. – Oxford: Blackwell, 2001. – 186 p.
3. Metaphor in cognitive linguistics / Ed. by R.W.Gibbs, G.Steen. – Amsterdam; Philadelphia: Benjamin's, 1999. – VIII, 233 p.
4. Boltakulova G. F. MEANS OF EXPRESSING AND ANALYZING ADVERBIAL MODIFIER OF TIME IN THE SENTENCE STRUCTURE IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN //DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPOKEN AND WRITTEN LANGUAGE AT THE CURRENT STAGE OF THE INTENSIVE INFORMATION TURNOVER. – 2015. – С. 11-12.
5. Farruxovna B. G., Ashirovich B. A. Pedagogical and Psychological Factors in the Membership of Individual Interest in the System of Continuous Education //JournalNX. – Т. 7. – №. 04. – С. 388-391.
6. Болтакулова Г. Ф. Способы выражения обстоятельства времени в английском и русском языках и его место в предложении //Молодой ученый. – 2015. – №. 14. – С. 583-585.
7. Ulugbekovna M. M. ENHANCING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL DEPARTMENTS //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 234-242.
8. Nomozova N. T. INNOVATIONS IN LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT: TRENDS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS //Экономика и социум. – 2024. – №. 6-2 (121). – С. 452-454.